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Evaluation Of Factors Influencing Air Quality In Sokoto Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

Air quality in Sokoto metropolis is influence by many factors, such as fuel combustion, refuse burning, dust re-suspension by motor vehicle, manufacturing and weather among others. Multivariate statistical analysis was used to determine the factors influencing air quality in Sokoto metropolis. Principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to 5 air quality parameters and 2 meteorological parameters for samples obtained from 10 sampling sites. PCA extracted 2 PCs namely anthropogenic and meteorological factors, which were responsible for more than 71% of the total variance of the metropolis. The cluster analysis indicated that three factors (anthropogenic emission, industrial activities and natural or weather factors) control the air quality of the area, and the variables were allocated to three groups based on similarity. A test of variance shows there is significant difference between the two seasons (wet/dry) for NO₂, SO₂ and CO, while there is no significant difference between PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. This work will provide policy makers and environmental managers with precise knowledge of air quality challenges affecting the metropolis and can also serve as a guide for air quality assessment of other areas that share similar characteristics.

Keywords: Air quality, Metropolis, Multivariate statistics, anthropogenic emission

INTRODUCTION

Air is the most important natural resources for nourishment and existence of life. Clean air is one of the major basic requirements for good human health. The air we breathe daily is comprised of 21% oxygen and 78% nitrogen, with the remaining consisting of trace amount of rare gasses. It becomes polluted by variety of sources which are natural or man- made activities (Patel et al., 2017). Air pollution is the presence in the atmosphere of one or more contaminants in such quantity and for such duration as to be injurious, or tend to be injurious to human health or welfare, animal or plant life (Obanya et al, 2018). Air pollution has been recognised as the most fatal form of pollution due to increasing pollution levels as a result of urbanization and growth. In 2012, the world health organisation estimates that 10% of global mortality, amounting to 7million people are as a result from air pollution (WHO, 2018). In the 2016 report, 2.9million annual death were reported of which more than 85% occurred in low and middle income countries (Saxena, 2020). This is a source of major concern to both modern and fast growing societies in the world to which Sokoto state is not an exception.

Anthropogenic activities such as indiscriminate disposal of waste from domestic, industrial and agricultural activities among others, contribute largely to pollution (Odunaike et al. 2008). Human activities, include become a major issue in many developing countries all over the world. The effects of the air pollutants and their synergistic interaction have not only put human and animal life at risk but also resulted in the loss of heritage, biodiversity, and property of national interest (Caselles, Colliga & Zornoza, 2002; Curtis, Rea, Smith, Fenyves & Pan, 2006).

Sokoto Metropolis is among the Nding burning of fossil fuels, industry, and transportation release pollutants such as NO₂, SO₂, PM, CO and Hydrocarbons into the air (Davis & Cornwell, 2008). Due to enhanced human activities producing increased emissions, atmospheric pollution in urban areas has,

igeria's urban areas that experience rapid growth and development due to rural-urban migration and proliferation of economic, political, social and cultural events (Eniolorunda & Dankani, 2012). These have led to increase in combustion of fossil fuel used for transportation, manufacturing, household energy consumption, use of power generators for commercial activities and refuse burning, these resulted in release of many harmful pollutant gasses into the environment (Nasiru, 2012). The presence of these pollutants in the atmosphere in high concentrations above permissible limits poses serious threat to public health and the environment (Leton, 2007). Thus CO, NO₂, SO₂, PM and meteorological parameters were selected to determine the factors influencing air quality in Sokoto Metropolis Sokoto state, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Sokoto Metropolis is located between latitudes 1301 10 11N to 1305 10 11N and longitudes 501310 11E to 5 01710 11E. It covers 16km radius from Shehu Kangiwa Square and is bounded by Kware Local Government to the North, Wamakko to the West, and Bodinga to the south, situated in the Sudan savanna (Olayinka, 2003). Sokoto Metropolis constitutes the whole of Sokoto North and Sokoto South Local Government Areas and parts of Dange/Shuni and Wamakko local government areas respectively. The area experiences two distinct seasons: the dry season (October–April) and wet season (May–September) (SOSG, 2011).

Figure 1 Study Area

Methods of Data collection: Sokoto metropolis was divided into twenty seven township wards under the jurisdictions of five local government areas, this is further sub divided into a number of smaller local areas by Sokoto State Primary Health Care Development Agency (SSPHCDA), and this was used to identify sampling points within the city. Five sampling points were selected purposively from commercial areas and another five points from residential areas. The commercial areas included are Gidan Man Ada, CBN Bridge, Old Market, Illela Garage and Dandima while the residential areas are Giginya Barracks, Unguwar Rogo, Kofar Taramniya, FGC Roundabout and Arkilla Housing. The primary data was collected using Bosean BH-4S Portable multi gas detector air sampler for detection of the gasses (SO₂, NO₂ and CO), and an air quality meter for the Particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), temperature and humidity. A hand held GPS (Global Positioning System Garmin GPS map 78s receiver) was used to obtain the coordinates of the sample locations. The data collection was carried out in four montshs, two months for each season (dry season and wet season) in two different periods of the day (morning 7:30am to 9:30am, Afternoon 12:00pm to 2:30pm and evening 4:30 to 6:30pm).

Methods of data analysis: Descriptive and multivariate statistical methods were employed to analyse SO₂, NO₂, CO, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and meteorological parameters (temperature and humidity) data obtained from the sampled sites. Descriptive statistics, specifically the mean and standard deviation, were calculated to summarize the data. The concentration of the pollutants were presented in a table to show the average, mean concentration and variation between periods of recorded emission levels. Multivariate statistical analysis was applied to 4 air quality and 2 meteorological parameters utilising Principal component analysis (PCA) and agglomerative hierarchical cluster to evaluate factors influencing air quality in Sokoto Metropolis.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA): Principal component analysis is a multivariate technique used to treat a set of variables together. PCA is the most widely used technique among the families of multivariate statistical analysis (Ranjan *et al.*, 2012). It is a technique that identifies patterns in data and presents them based on their similarities and differences. Delineating patterns in data with a complex relation is not an easy task, thus utilizing PCA in such a case (for example, air quality) would provide a reliable result (Smith, 2012). The main aim of PCA is to summarize a multivariate dataset by reducing the statistical noise in the data, exposing the outlier, and then arranging the components in descending order (from the largest contributor to the least) as accurately as possible with as few principal components as possible (Pitkanen *et al.*, 2004). Normally the first few PCs will interpret the variables with the highest variance in the case of large differences in variance. Variables are normalized individually to unit variance and, as such, contribute equally when the correlation matrix is used (Farnhama *et al.*, 2003).

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) was first conducted for suitability of PCA, and this is to evaluate the suitability of PCA and to test the adequacy of samples. It is always advisable to proceed to the next level if the KMO value is 0.5 and above (Mustapha & Aris, 2012). In this study the KMO was found to be 0.6149 for the data. PCA extracts variables into groups known as principal components (PCs), with their eigenvalues, variability (%) and cumulative values (%) of individual and collective PCs, and these are used to plot a graph from which the PCs with eigenvalue greater than 1 are retained. In addition, Bartlett's test for sphericity shows significant results ($p > 0.0001$). This indicates that sampling adequacy is highly suitable for PCA (Field, 2017).

Cluster analysis: is a multivariate statistical method that classify variables into groups called clusters based on their similarity to each other and dissimilarity to other groups. This classification is done objectively without prior assumptions regarding the data so as to uncover structure or underlying patterns of the original data set (Yu, 2005), here cluster analysis was applied to the air pollutant gasses, particulate matter and meteorological parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The descriptive statistics for air pollutants and meteorological parameters including mean, median, minimum, maximum and standard deviation for dry season Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for air quality data in dry season

Variable	Observations	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. deviation
PM2.5	30	18.6667	77.7667	46.029	17.5290
PM10	30	22.0000	98.4333	53.259	23.9346
NO2	30	0.0333	0.5667	0.2406	0.1485
SO2	30	0.0000	0.0867	0.0203	0.0272
CO	30	1.1000	52.3333	8.2122	10.0750
TEMP	30	25.9333	37.1333	32.749	2.7856
HUM	30	15.0000	27.6333	16.469	2.5559

The Kaisers criterion, also known as the eigenvalue-one criterion, is one of the most used criteria for solving the number of components challenges in PCA (Voukantsis et al, 2012), one should only retain and interpret any component with an eigenvalue greater than 1.00. This is because each of the observed variables contributes one unit of variance to the total variation in the data set. As such any component that shows an eigenvalue greater than 1.00 is believed to be responsible for a greater amount of variation than is contributed by one variable. Thus a component with such a characteristics is responsible for a significant amount of variance to be retained, whereas a component with an eigenvalue less than 1.00 is responsible for less variation than is contributed by one variable. Though, the main aim of PCA is to decrease the number of observed variables to a relatively smaller number of components without jeopardizing the actual interpretation of the data in question, therefore retaining components that account for less variance than contributed by individual variables defeats the aim of PCA. For this reason, components with eigenvalue less than 1.00 are viewed as trivial and are not retained (Yu, 2005).

For air quality in dry season, PCA generated two components of eigenvalues greater than one after varimax rotation. These components explained 68.0829% of air quality variation in the study (Table 2).

Table 2: Factor loading after varimax rotations

Parameter	PC1	PC2
PM2.5	0.9168	-0.1585
PM10	0.9491	-0.1445
NO2	0.2066	-0.2480
SO2	-0.0358	0.2066
CO	0.6656	0.4729
TEMP	-0.2519	0.7820
HUM	-0.0048	-0.8492
Eigenvalue	2.8989	1.8669
Variability%	41.4122	26.6707
Cumulative%	41.4122	68.0829

PC1 explained 41.4 % of the variance in air quality versus 26.7 % for PC2. PM_{2.5} has the highest loading in this PC with 0.9168 followed by PM₁₀ with 0.94991 (table 2). Particulate matter is produced from naturally occurring dust and pollen as well as soot and aerosols from combustion activities such as agricultural burning, transportation, manufacturing, and power generation (Langner, Draheim & Endlicher, 2011). Consequently, its concentrations will vary with traffic volume of diesel engines, burning of tyres, the cement company at the site, couple with the power generation plant in

the area and also demolition/construction at the site (Oji & Adamu, 2020). CO is loaded on this PC with a value of 0.6656. It is the result of incomplete combustion of fuel in vehicle engine due to acceleration, load and poor maintenance. Its concentration varied with traffic circulation level and air/fuel ratio (Ariko *et al*, 2014). Furthermore, the vehicles at the nearby traffic light intersection are in inactive position with engine exuded more CO compared to free flow condition and also the power generators at the site (Akinyemi & Usikalu, 2013). Furthermore, PC1 consists of strong positive contributions of traffic originated emissions of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and CO (Papamanolis, 2015). These results indicate that this PC represents the traffic/industrial pollution.

PC2 represents global warming gas as CO and temperature were loaded on it with values 0.47729 and 0.7820 which is moderate and strong contribution respectively. It represents about more than halve the variance in air quality of PC1 and accounts for 26.7 %. The main source of CO is the fuel combustion in vehicles. It is a product of incomplete combustion of hydrocarbons (such as fuel, gasoline, natural gas and coal) and occurs when carbon in the fuel is partially oxidized rather than fully oxidized to carbon dioxide (CO₂) while the compound exists naturally, it has likely been present since early in the earth's formation (Chichkova & Prockop, 2011). Consequently, its concentration will vary due to temperature which maximise the vertical mixing, resulted in higher concentrations of CO during dry season. High temperature during the dry season enhances the vertical mixing and increase of mixing height that account the high concentration of the pollutants (Oji & Adamu, 2020).

The descriptive statistics for air pollutants and meteorological parameters including mean, median, minimum, maximum and standard deviation for wet season Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for air Quality data for wet season

Variable	Observations	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. deviation
PM2.5	30	18.5333	130.6667	51.1711	27.6491
PM10	30	17.6667	126.1000	52.6656	29.4881
NO2	30	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
SO2	30	0.0000	0.0333	0.0011	0.0061
CO	30	4.5333	48.6667	13.3944	11.0366
TEMP	30	22.5333	44.6667	29.7533	3.9767
HUM	30	44.6667	80.1000	61.4633	10.1261

For wet season, PCA extracted two components accounts for 71 % of air quality variation in the study site (table 4). Three air pollutants are loaded on PC1 versus two meteorological parameters on PC2. PM_{2.5} 0.9049, PM₁₀ 0.9085, and CO 0.8538 are loaded on PC1 positively. The contributions of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} in this PC explained that there exists re-suspension of coarse particles. According to Khodier et al, (2012) high PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentration most probably related re-suspension of particles. The re-suspension particles come mainly from street dust and road surfaces (Voukantsis et al., 2012). CO also loaded positively and can be attributed to engine emission from vehicles in most part of sites. Hence, PC1 is related with the re-suspension of particulates and emission from vehicles engine are the main source of these pollutants and also open burning activity around the study area. Therefore, this PC may be called traffic pollution or fossil fuel combustion component.

PC2 is associated with contribution from meteorological parameters, with strong negative and strong positive correlation. Temperature loaded -0.8693 and humidity 0.8851 (inverse relationship). The contributions of meteorological parameters in PC2 for all sites thus associated with meteorological factors (Awang *et al*, 2015). The percent of contribution of PC2 was 23.5966%.

Table 4: Factor loadings after varimax rotation

Parameter	PC1	PC2
PM2.5	0.9049	0.2613
PM10	0.9085	0.3194
NO2	0.0000	0.0000
SO2	0.1391	0.1738
CO	0.8538	-0.1582
TEMP	-0.0975	-0.8693
HUM	0.1327	0.8851
Eigenvalue	2.8482	1.4158
Variability%	47.4703	23.5966
Cumulative%	47.4703	71.0669

Table 5: Mean Seasonal Variations of Gaseous and Particulate Matter

Parameters	Seasons		P-value	Mean value
	Wet	Dry		
PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	51.17±36.22	46.03±24.09	0.264	48.6±30.78
PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	52.67±38.34	53.26±34.19	0.913	52.96±36.22
NO ₂ (ppm)	0.00±0.00	0.24±0.19	0.000	0.12±0.18
SO ₂ (ppm)	0.00±0.01	0.02±0.04	0.000	0.01±0.03
CO (ppm)	13.39±12.45	8.21±11.4	0.004	10.80±12.19

Table 5 shows the test of variance at 0.05 level of significance between the pollutants concentrations in wet and dry season. The statistics shows there exists a significant difference between the seasons (wet and dry) for NO₂, SO₂ and CO. This is because the calculated P-value of 0.00, 0.00 and 0.004 were found to be lower than 0.05 level of significance (Thomas, 2014). However, there is no significant difference in the reading of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ because the calculated P value of 0.264 and 0.913 was found to be greater than the 0.05 level of significance (Zalakeviciute *et al*, 2020).

Fig 2: Dendrogram base on the clustering of air quality data for dry season

Cluster analysis was applied to the air quality data of dry season and the resulting factors were classified into three major groups based on the similarities among the parameters and dissimilarities to other groups. The first group as shown in Figure 2, consists of SO₂ and TEMP. Cluster 2 consist of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and CO and Cluster 3 consist of humidity and NO₂. The first cluster consist of pollutant gas and meteorological parameter. The second cluster is of particulates except CO which is gaseous pollutants. The last cluster is gaseous and meteorological parameter. Thus, the first cluster is associated with anthropogenic emission from incomplete combustion of fuel containing sulphur oxide and temperature which influence SO₂, NO₂ and humidity (Doreena *et al*, 2012). The second cluster

contain PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and CO. This group explain the industrial activities, high traffic of diesel engines and open burning which rises particulate pollutants and CO (Khodier *et al*, 2012). The third cluster contain humidity and NO₂ and humidity strongly influenced all the parameters (NO₂, SO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and CO) as natural factor (Oji & Adamu, 2020). NO₂ is the result of vehicular emission due to high traffic and industrial activities at the site.

Fig 3: Dendrogram based on the clustering of air quality data for wet season

The result obtained by CA detected the similarity groups yielding a dendrogram into three statistically significant clusters, particulate pollutants, gaseous pollutants and meteorological parameter. The dendrogram resulting from agglomerative hierarchical CA showing the spatial clustering during wet season as shown in Fig 3. The first cluster as shown in Figure 3, consists of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} are related to particulate and gases which are emitted by motor vehicles or result from industrial activity around the study areas. PM can also be formed through open burning and soil dust emissions around the sampling points (Olayinka *et al*, 2012). Cluster II consist of one parameter which is humidity. This cluster can be categorized as weather or natural factor because virtually all the clusters are directly or indirectly associated with weather. The last cluster consist of temperature only which is categorise as weather or natural factor that virtually influence all other clusters, as high temperature lowers humidity, and it also rises gaseous pollutants (Olayinka *et al*, 2012).

CONCLUSIONS

Air pollutants and meteorological parameters of Sokoto metropolis were successfully analysed with PCA and HCA to determine factors influencing air quality of the area. The air quality of the metropolis was found to be influenced by five factors, namely PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO and meteorological factors in dry/wet season. PCA results suggest that the first component is the highest and the most influential factor regarding the air pollution, and it involves multiple process (naturally occurring dust, pollen and soot) the dominant is the soot. Except for CO that was characterized as the PC2 source from anthropogenic activities. PC2 was found to be influence by CO and natural or meteorological factors (temperature and humidity) respectively. The resulting output of HCA justified the earlier interpretation of the influencing factors by PCA. The seasonal variation shows there exists a significant difference between the seasons (wet and dry) for NO₂, SO₂ and CO. while there is no significant difference for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀.

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